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ABSTRACTS

increasing number of planes of the deformity. No significant difference was found in terms of complications.

Conclusion: Smart Correction fixator is an accurate device with ease of application and planning. It shows higher accuracy for correcting deformities according to Ilizarov external fixator. With increasing number of planes, difference between two devices become higher. Relation between complexity of the deformity and residual deformity will possibly be statistically better in favor of Smart Correction with larger study groups.

**O 013. Appliance of Ilizarov apparatus in treatment of tibial plateau fractures
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Abstract Body : Aims: We restricted our work on treatment of open and closed tibial plateau fractures, of different gradings and classifications, with the Ilizarov apparatus.

Materialand methods: In our clinic, from the period of 2006 to 2012, 40 patients with tibial plateau fractures were treated using the Ilizarov apparatus. Of these, 30 were males and 10 females. From that ammount, 8 of them had open, and 32 had closed fractures. We used Anderson-Gustillo classification for open fractures, and Schatzker classification for closed fractures. For fracture types II and III we performed lifting of the depressed plateau using the elevator and metaphyseal bone graft. Stabilization of the plateau after the reconstruction was done using needles with oliva and setting the ring of the device with streched needles. In six cases we used the assisted arthroscopy. In four cases, we used preoperative angiography. Average wearing time of the apparatus was 3 (2.5 to 3.5) months. Successive standing was allowed immediately after the surgery (10% of BW), and was increased weekly by 15% of body weight.

Results: Complete reconstruction of the tibia plateau was achieved in 34 treated patients with good results. In six patients we had an infection around the pins of the device which was taken care of with antibiotics based on smear findings. In four cases we had common fibular nerve lesions, (Schatzker V and VI), of transitory nature, which restituted after 6 months, verified with EMNG. Four patients (Schatzker V and VI), had incongruity of articular surface of the plateau. Pseudoarthrosis of the upper part of the tibia was present in two cases.

Conclusion: Our experience shows, that using the Ilizarov method benefits with good reconstruction of the tibial plateau, avoidance of major operative incisions, blood loss and minimal risk of infection.

**O 014. Cost analysis of complex tibial fractures treated with circular frames
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Abstract Body : Background: We discuss the cost analysis of 200 tibial fractures treated with illizarov or taylor spatial frames. The purpose of this